

New records of Longhorn Beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Peru

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, longhorn beetles, zoogeography, new records, Peru, South America.

Abstract. In this work, 16 species from 13 tribes and 2 subfamilies of Cerambycidae are reported for the first time for Peru (South America).

Introduction

New scientific studies on the Cerambycidae family in South America have been appearing quite frequently recently. This demonstrates that the fauna of many regions remains insufficiently studied. The Peruvian fauna of longhorn beetles is no exception, continuing to surprise with new discoveries for the country. The Cerambycidae family in Peruvian fauna consists of eight subfamilies: Agapanthiinae, Anoplodermatinae, Cerambycinae, Disteniinae, Lamiinae, Lepturinae, Parandrinae, and Prioninae. Peru is striking in its diversity; 1,138 species have currently been recorded for this region (Tavakilian & Chevillotte, 2025). Here we present several new discoveries for Peru.

Material and method

The species identification of the longhorn beetles was performed by the author. Photographs of the beetles were taken using an Olympus SZX7 stereomicroscope with an integrated Olympus SC180 camera. Olympus cellSens Entry 3.1 (Build 21199) software was used. Digital processing of the photographs was performed using Photorom.

* The language of the article has been preserved in the author's version.

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Results

Cerambycinae Latreille, 1802
Achrysonini Lacordaire, 1869

Achryson immaculipenne Gounelle, 1909
Fig. 1

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Brazil. Currently, it is known from Argentina, Brazil, Bolivia, Venezuela, Guyana, Colombia, Paraguay and, Ecuador.

Callidiopini Lacordaire, 1868
Curtomerus purus Martins, 1974
Fig. 2

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 07-12.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Bolivia and until now was indicated only for this country.

Cerambycini Latreille, 1804

Sphalotrichus puncticollis (Bates, 1870)

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo distr., Satipo, 09.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described based from Brazil. Currently, it is known from Bolivia, Brazil, Guyana and Panama. For Peru, the literary source lists its subspecies *S. puncticollis robustus* (Bates, 1872).

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Clytini Mulsant, 1839

Mecometopus hauseri Bezark, Santos-Silva & Galileo, 2016
Fig. 3

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 07-12.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Bolivia and until now was indicated only for this country.

Obrini Mulsant, 1839

Obrium trifasciatum Bosq, 1951

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Argentina. Currently, it is known from Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Guyana and Uruguay.

Rhinotragini Thomson, 1861

Ecliptoides pilosipes (Peñaherrera & Tavakilian, 2004)
Fig. 4

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, A.V. Petrov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Guyana. Currently, it is known from Brazil and Guyana.

Tomopterus grossefoveolatus Zajciw, 1964

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 07-12.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Brazil. Currently, it is known from Brazil, Guyane and Panama.

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Tropidini Martins and Galileo, 2007

Compsibidion fairmairei (Thomson, 1865)

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Chile. Currently, it is known from Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Paraguay and Uruguay.

Lamiinae Latreille, 1825

Acanthocinini Blanchard, 1845

Nyssodrysternum cingillum Monné, 2009

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 01.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described based from Bolivia. Currently, it is known from Bolivia and Guyana.

Sternacutus nyssodroides (Tippmann, 1960)

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described based from Bolivia. Currently, it is known from Bolivia and Ecuador.

Acanthoderini J. Thomson, 1860

Aegomorphus consentaneus (Thomson, 1865)

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 29.09.2024, 07-12.10.2024, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Brazil. Currently, it is known from Bolivia, Brazil and Ecuador.

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Dufauxia guaicurana Lane, 1955

Fig. 5

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Puerto Ocopa, 10.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Brazil. Currently, it is known from Bolivia, Brazil and Paraguay.

Agapanthiini Mulsant, 1839

Hippopsis apicalis (Bates, 1866)

Fig. 6

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Brazil. Currently, it is known from Bolivia, Brazil, Guyana and Ecuador.

Calliini Thomson, 1864

Eumimesis decoratus (Fuchs, 1955)

Fig. 7

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 29.09.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Bolivia and until now was indicated only for this country.

Desmiphorini Thomson, 1860

Ischnoleomimus arriagadai Galileo & Martins, 2004

Material examined. Peru, Ucayali reg., Atalaya prov., Pitzá 02.2024, local collector leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Paraguay and until now was indicated only for this country.

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Fig. 1. *Achryson immaculipenne* Gounelle, 1909: male, Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg. **Fig. 2.** *Curtoemerus purus* Martins, 1974: male, Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 07-12.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg. **Fig. 3.** *Mecometopus hauseri* Bezark, Santos-Silva & Galileo, 2016: female, Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 07-12.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg. **Fig. 4.** *Ecliptoides pilosipes* (Peñaherrera & Tavakilian, 2004): female, Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, A.V. Petrov leg. **Fig. 5.** male, Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Puerto Ocopa, 10.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg. **Fig. 6.** *Hippopsis apicalis* (Bates, 1866): male, Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 14-16.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

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Onciderini Thomson, 1860

Tulcus fulvofasciatus (Dillon & Dillon, 1945)

Material examined. Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 07-12.10.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Remarks. This species was described from Colombia. Currently, it is known from Colombia, Costa Rica and Panama.

Fig. 7. *Eumimesis decoratus* (Fuchs, 1955): male, Peru, Junin reg., Satipo prov., Rio Venado, 29.09.2024, D.A. Kuleshov leg.

Conclusion

Even in regions where extensive collections have been conducted in the past, previously uncollected species are often encountered. Based on a study of Cerambycidae materials stored in the author's collection, new data are presented on 16 species of longhorn beetles from Peru.

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Acknowledgments. The author expresses sincere gratitude to his expedition colleagues Alexander Petrov and Sergey Mukhanov. The author is especially grateful to Alain Audureau for consultations and assistance in identifying some Cerambycidae.

REFERENCES

- Aguilar C., Cubilla F., Avila-Torres I. & Garcete-Barrett B. 2024. Two new records of Cerambycinae (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Peru. - *Acta Zoológica Lilloana*. 68 (1): 59-67.
- Audureau A. 2012. Notes sur les Onciderini du Pérou (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, Onciderini). - *Les Cahiers Magellanes (NS)*. 9: 57-64.
- Audureau A. 2016. Notes sur les Apomecynini du Pérou (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae). *Les Cahiers Magellanes (NS)*. 23: 60-68.
- Audureau A. & Demez P. 2015. Nouvelles especes d Acanthocinini neotropicaux originaires du Perou. - *Les Cahiers Magellanes (NS)*. 18: 19-26.
- Demez P. & Touroult J. 2011. Contribution a la connaissance des longicornes du Perou I 59 nouveaux signalements pour le pays (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - *Les Cahiers Magellanes (NS)*. 6: 97-108.
- Galileo M., Martins U., Le Tirant S. & Santos-Silva A. 2014. Five new species of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) from Peru and Bolivia and two new records for Peru. - *Insecta Mundi* .0376: 1-13.
- Juárez-Noé G. 2025. New records of Cerambycidae (Insecta, Coleoptera) from Peru. - *Boletín del Museo Nacional de Historia Natural del Paraguay*. 29 (Art. e2025007): 11 pp.
- Juárez-Noé G. & Fagerstrom C. 2024. An annotated and illustrated catalog of the Peruvian specimens of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) housed in the Biological Museum at Lund University, Sweden. - *Zootaxa*. 5514 (4): 368-384.
- Monne M. & Chaboo C. 2015. Beetles (Coleoptera) of Peru: A Survey of the Families. Cerambycidae, Disteniidae, Vesperidae. - *Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society*. 88 (1): 34-120.
- Monné M., Nearn E., Carril S., Swift I. & Monne M. 2012. Preliminary checklist of the Cerambycidae, Disteniidae, and Vesperidae (Coleoptera) of Peru. - *Insecta Mundi*. 0213: 1-48.
- Tavakilian G. (Systematics) & Chevillotte H. (Webmaster) 2025. Titan database about Longhorns or Timber-Beetles (Cerambycidae). - URL: http://titan.gbif.fr/accueil_uk.html (date of access 12.10.2025)

Received: 07.11.2025

Accepted: 12.12.2025